

Perioperative Glycemic Management and Protocol

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Background

Diabetes

- Intraoperative hyperglycemia associated with infections, sepsis, CVA and AKI
- Intraoperative hyperglycemia strongly predicts postoperative hyperglycemia

Class of 2021 DNP Project Results:

- Retrospective chart review of 100 patients with DM2, case length >2 hr.
- Only 3% of patients had BG levels measured intraoperatively
- No consistency in type of insulin given

Purpose

To develop a Perioperative Glycemic Management Protocol and educate anesthesia providers on that protocol.

Methods

Design:

- Educational intervention for anesthesia providers, supplemented by an evidence-based perioperative glycemic management protocol

Setting:

- A virtual meeting via Microsoft Teams at Kaiser Permanente, Orange County Medical Center

Sample:

- Certified Registered Nurse Anesthetists

Measures:

- Acceptance of proposed protocol by stakeholders, pre/post education tests, evaluation tools

Conceptual Framework

The Iowa Model Revised: The Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Health Care

Perioperative Glycemic Protocol

Perioperative Insulin Guidelines

1. All diabetic patients should have BG checked in the preoperative area
2. Diabetic patients who are on pharmacologic management to have BG checked q2h in the OR
3. BG >180 mg/dL treated with SQ rapid-acting insulin within 30 mins
4. Consider insulin drip if BG >300 mg/dL, if patient is critically ill or if longer procedure

Perioperative Hypoglycemic Protocol

1. Hold insulin drip if started
2. BG 41-70: Give 1/3 amp of D50
3. BG < 40: Give 1 amp D50
4. Repeat BG q15m until BG >70 mg/dL; then q30m until BG >110 mg/dL
5. Once BG >110 mg/dL, check BG hourly & restart infusion at 1/2 rate once BG >180 mg/dL

Perioperative SQ Rapid-acting Insulin Dosing or Starting Rate for Insulin Infusion

BG (mg/dl)	Insulin Sensitive(2)	Usual Insulin	Insulin Resistant(3)
141-180	0 units	2 units	3 units
181-220	2 units	3 units	4 units
221-260	3 units	4 units	5 units
261-300	4 units	6 units	8 units
301-350	5 units	8 units	10 units
351-400	6 units	10 units	12 units
>400	8 units	12 units	14 units

Note: Consider Insulin Infusion for BG >300; Insulin sensitive: Age >70, GFR <45, no hx DM; Insulin resistant: BMI >35, home insulin >800U/day, steroids >20mg Prednisone daily

Protocol also includes insulin drip titration table

Results

Kaiser Permanente- Orange County to Implement Proposed Protocol

Education Intervention Test Results

Discussion

Discussion of Results

- Stakeholders at the project site recognize importance of implementing protocol
- Unreliable posttest scores due to small sample
- Virtual learning and inability to ensure attentiveness may impact learning
- Post-education discussion included possible barriers to implementation

Study Limitations

- Small sample size of 22 CRNAs and 1 Anesthesia Department Administrator
- Project site declined use of a positive feedback system or CE credits

Potential Implementation Plan

1. Identify **barriers** to implementation
2. Collect additional **data** to support protocol implementation
3. Identify project site **team leader** and adjust protocol
4. Collaborate with **pharmacy** to obtain access to rapid-acting insulin in OR
5. Project site to **require** anesthesia providers to complete virtual **educational module**
6. Provide **CE credit** for module completion
7. Develop a **decision support tool**